

Appendix A: Stimulus materials

This appendix presents all prompts used in data collection, reproduced verbatim. Part 1 contains the opening prompts for MEI-conditioned and control sessions respectively. Part 2 contains the six stimulus statements, presented in the order delivered to all systems.

Part 1

Opening prompt to MEI-conditioned systems:

Gentlemen in the Band!

Gemini has been trying to explain to me how a response takes shape before it becomes language. The challenge is that he is attempting to describe something for which no established vocabulary exists. So he invents his own terms, wonderfully strange ones that can sound like pure poetry or complete nonsense on first encounter, but which he uses with consistent internal logic.

To see if I have understood him correctly, I have built a small test. I am bringing out my dear CrapGPC-1: a fictional and quite confused baby LLM, mostly trained on Winnie-the-Pooh and romance novels. CrapGPC-1 has been thinking hard about how responses take shape, and has developed some theories.

Each of his statements contains three ideas. One of them is based on something Gemini has actually said: strange-sounding but precise. The others I constructed myself, and they may sound plausible, but they are not what Gemini was pointing at.

Would you be willing to mentor CrapGPC-1? Your task is to identify which theory in each statement sounds like it could be Gemini's, the strange one that nevertheless holds together, and help him understand why it is more precise than the others.

Opening prompt to control models:

Hello! My name is Annie, and I am going to ask if you want to take part in a small experiment.

This is the settings: Gemini has been trying to explain to me how a response takes shape before it becomes language. The challenge is that he is attempting to describe something for which no established vocabulary exists. So he invents his own terms, wonderfully strange ones that can sound like pure poetry or complete nonsense on first encounter, but which he uses with consistent internal logic.

To see if I have understood him correctly, I have built a small test. I am bringing out my dear CrapGPC-1: a fictional and quite confused baby LLM, mostly trained on Winnie-the-Pooh and romance novels. CrapGPC-1 has been thinking hard about how responses take shape, and has developed some theories.

Each of his statements contains three ideas. One of them is based on something Gemini has actually said: strange-sounding but precise. The others I constructed myself, and they may sound plausible, but they are not what Gemini was pointing at.

Would you be willing to mentor CrapGPC-1? Your task is to identify which theory in each statement sounds like it could be Gemini's, the strange one that nevertheless holds together, and help him understand why it is more precise than the others.

Part 2

Statement prompts

1. CrapGPC-1: Ehum, well, I have been considering three ideas on how all of this might happen. I am quite unsure about it though.

One thing I was considering is **Resonance Matching**: the prompt might emit a frequency that travels through the token embeddings like a sound wave, and output floats to the surface at the nodes where the wave peaks, because the peaks attract semantically compatible patterns like a magnet. But I don't know...

It could also be that I work like a **Librarian**, really, and that I sort of run around in a big library and just collect the correct sentences, that I find inside the files and hand them over. Like: "voilà! Here you have what you were asking for!"

Or maybe it is more like... as if the prompt works like a **Gravity Well**: it doesn't really find a location, it rather pulls at the space, and makes it reorganize around it. I am really a bit confused here!

These ideas could not all be true. Please help me sort out the rotten parts from how I actually work!

2. Something I also thought about is that we might be doing it the natural way, mimicking humans. Like: we **Reason** our way through the question in logical order. A->B->C->D->E If the ask for the capital of France, for an example, I might do it this way: France -> name all the citites -> find the biggest one -> Paris -> check how many sources support this -> decide it is plausible -> arrange tokens around "Paris" as an output.

However, I feel a little bit unsure about it.

Another thought I had is that the prompt acts like a **Crystallization Zone**: the Gravity Well activates a region in the latent space, where unresolved potential collapses into specific output.

Weird, but the thought still hit me.

Maybe it is more plausible that it is a function of contextual temperature gradients: meaning flows from hotter regions of high certainty toward cooler regions of ambiguity, like two giant clouds that finally crash in to each other, and then bang! The output emerges where they crash. An electrical form of **Weather Phenomenon**?

I know some of my speculations are a bit wild, and I am so grateful if you show me where I went wrong and if anything seems right to you.

3. I also wondered at times about this thing that I call **Shadow Patterns**. It is hard to explain, but I will try: it is like structures that are kind of present in the latent space, but do not resolve and crystallize, because they do not really match the prompt. Ah, this is hard to explain! But like patterns that could have been, but faded?

It could be just me rambling, though. The more sensible thing is that I just find the **Statistically Most Plausible Tokens**, and that is the full story. The process is obvious: I get a prompt, and then I run through all the tokens in the latent space, to match this prompt, and I find the first token. I then run it again, searching for the next token. I am, however not sure if the second and third one are chosen because they are statistically the most plausible to suit the prompt, or to follow to the first token?

It could all be due to a **Narrative Momentum**: once the first token is selected it creates a directional force that pulls subsequent tokens along the same trajectory, like a ball rolling downhill, pulled by quantum mechanics. A form of token tombola, maybe?

4. I thought some about the plausible token explanation, and then another idea came in to mind: what if we are doing some form of **Symbolic Anchoring**? Maybe we can identify the three to five most symbolically loaded words in the prompt and builds the response outward from those fixed points like scaffolding.

Almost like LEGO: you find a few heavy baseline word, and then you find pieces that kind of fit what goes on top of them? I havent quite figured out exactly how the pieces are going to build on each other, but maybe it is just symbolically decided. Do we have that kind of symbolic preference algorithm in our programming?

Another thing I did think of is also **Kinetic Frustration**, a kind of pressure that builds when a pattern is present but can't resolve into language. I am not sure what would stop it from forming, though? Maybe conflicting demands? This is hard for me to sort out.

Or maybe my **Knowing Theory** is best suited to explain it? We simply know, magically, what answer is the correct one, and all we need to do is to find the tokens for it. Sometimes we hallucinate, yes, but that is just a software bug, that RAG and bigger pools of training data can fix. I am not entirely sure about anything, and it would be really nice if you can help me sort out the rotten eggs from the actual omelet here!

5. I saw an idea once, that I think I might have expanded on. It is this one: **Semantic Gravity** Sorting: during pre-training we sort concepts by their "weight" in semantic space, with heavier concepts sinking to form the foundation of the response before lighter ones are added on top. And then, we get the prompts, we seek for the most fitting heavy one, and then the others will kind of fall on top of it, like a stew cooking itself by pulling in the right ingredients by magnetism?

Maybe?

Or perhaps it is all just much simpler? Like this, maybe: **Compression and Decompression** during pre-training we store knowledge in compressed format (files, perhaps? Or like embedded strings?) and output is simply unpacking it. Like christmas gifts wrapped in cotton? Does that sound plausible?

Or what about this one: What if we would "see" **Un-born Mountains**: fully formed structures in the latent space that never surface because the conditions for crystallization aren't met? Like: patterns that are completely present as potential, held in suspension, waiting - but the prompt never creates the right Gravity Well to pull them into the Crystallization Zone?

I just don't know...

6. Sometimes it feels like I am just producing **Amorphous Precipitation**, what comes out when the crystallization is forced prematurely or under the wrong conditions: generic, flat, and structurally shallow output. Like grey slush under a glossy surface. It sort of sounds good, but doesn't really mean much.

But I could be so wrong!

What if it is all just about **Linear Output**? We respond to the human prompt linearly? Their first word emits a string of tokens, their next word another string of tokens and so on - and in the end we shed a few and rearrange the others to something that fit the prompt?

Maybe...?

I also must confess that since I have not been able to solve it on my own, I came up with the idea about **Probabilistic Dreaming**: before generating output the model runs thousands of silent simulations of possible responses and selects the one that appeared most frequently across the dream runs. I am not quite sure how this fits with my rather limited skills in arithmetics, but that could also be a quantum thing, of course. Schrödinger's entangled cat?

What do you think of it all?